

Views and Experiences of Selected Master Teachers in Quezon Province in Conducting School Learning Action Cell

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Abstract

This research explored the views and experiences of selected master teachers in Quezon Province in conducting School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) and how these experiences influence teacher collaboration, professional growth, and instructional improvement. The study specifically focused on SLAC implementation in five dimensions: instructional support, curriculum implementation, learning delivery, professional development, and classroom assessment. It also identified the challenges encountered by master teachers in SLAC facilitation, the coping strategies they employed, and the professional opportunities that emerged through this school-based continuing professional development mechanism. Using interpretative phenomenological analysis, 15 master teachers were purposively selected as co-researchers across various schools in Quezon Province. Data were collected through in-depth interviews and thematic analysis was employed to interpret emerging patterns. Findings revealed that SLACs serve as a dynamic platform for delivering instructional support by providing teachers with hands-on, practical strategies to improve teaching. In terms of curriculum implementation, master teachers reported that SLACs enhance curriculum alignment, lesson planning, and contextualization of content. For

learning delivery, SLACs were instrumental in sharing differentiated strategies and promoting inclusive and adaptive practices. As for professional development, the sessions cultivated peer mentoring, reflection, and shared accountability. On classroom assessment, master teachers facilitated collaborative review and improvement of formative and summative tools aligned with learning competencies. Despite these gains, significant challenges include time constraints, lack of resources, overlapping schedules, and varying teacher engagement. These were addressed through proactive planning, feedback mechanisms, collaborative leadership, and strategic alignment with school goals. The implementation of SLACs generated professional opportunities such as enhanced instructional leadership, improved peer relationships, and increased confidence in facilitating teacher learning. It was concluded that SLACs positively influence teacher collaboration, foster professional growth, and lead to instructional improvements when implemented consistently, responsively, and reflectively. It is recommended that the Schools Division Offices and school heads provide structured support, adequate resources, and scheduled time to sustain the SLAC initiative.

Keywords: *classroom assessment, instructional support, master teachers, professional development, school learning action cell*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has mandated the establishment of School Learning Action Cells (SLACs), which are crucial professional development tools designed to promote ongoing enhancement of teaching methods by means of teacher collaboration and reflective learning (DepEd Order No. 35, 2016). The purpose of these action cells is to enable an effective and efficient teaching-learning process by providing an opportunity for identifying and prioritizing the requirements that must be addressed immediately for the benefit of both teachers and students. As the foundation and core of the Department of Education, SLACs are intended to serve as a support network for educators entrusted with providing fundamental, high-quality instruction.

The first step in the implementation of SLAC is the assessment of the needs of the teachers, which is usually based on the Electronic Self-Assessment Tool (ESAT). Teachers answer the ESAT every end of the school year so that the master teachers can plan the topic for the next school year. After analyzing the results of ESAT, master teachers prioritize the topics that urgently need to be addressed. This calls for the formulation of school learning action, which is the next step. All teachers must be part of the SLAC. SLAC could be composed of five to fifteen members, depending on the population of teachers as well as the urgency of the problem. A school may organize as many LACs as may be deemed necessary depending on the identified needs of the school. In all schools, teachers may convene in groups that are strategically decided. These may be by key stage, grade level, learning area, or programs offered by the school. Multigrade schools may be clustered in different ways by the district or division supervisors based on the objectives of the LACs to be conducted (DepEd Order no. 35, s 2016).

The number, duration, and schedule of meetings are up to the LAC members. Although it is highly advised to devote one to two hours per week, the diversity of teaching conditions may not always accommodate this. To serve as documentation, LAC sessions are recorded through LAC plans where the LAC process is stated. On the other hand, LAC meetings ought to take place at least once every month (DepEd, 2016).

Sharing best practices, addressing teaching issues, and coordinating instructional tactics with national education standards—such as the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST)—are all made possible by SLACs. Teachers are able to work together to address shared difficulties because these professional learning communities cultivate a culture of reflection and shared accountability. For SLACs to be successful, opportunities for collaboration and professional development are essential (Dela Cruz & Santos, 2017). According to research, when used properly, SLACs greatly improve teacher cooperation and instructional strategies, which eventually improves student learning results (Garcia & Torres, 2021).

As mentors and instructional leaders, master teachers are crucial to the implementation of SLAC. They are in charge of facilitating discussions, organizing sessions, and making sure that everything is in line with DepEd guidelines and school objectives (Reyes, 2019). Similarly, master teachers are essential in fostering an environment of learning where educators are encouraged to share their knowledge and come up with innovative solutions to problems in the classroom (Reyes, 2019). The study adds to the larger conversation on successful professional growth by figuring out how experienced educators take advantage of these chances. The opportunities identified in SLAC implementation highlight the potential for innovation and collaboration. Through the master teachers' leadership and mentorship, they create a ripple effect that influences the professional growth of their colleagues and, ultimately, the learning outcomes of students (Reyes, 2019). Documenting these opportunities provides a roadmap for scaling up successful initiatives.

Despite its pleasing principles and ideal design, challenges arise in implementing SLACs properly in the grassroots. Even with a well-versed plan, problems arise in the implementation of the said plan

(Amarillo, 2020; Almorcar & Padasas, 2022). Moreover, despite the essential role of master teachers, they encounter various challenges, including time constraints, lack of resources, and uneven teacher participation (Amarillo, 2020). Almonicar and Padasas (2022) stated that some challenges in SLAC implementation are the schedule of the school learning action cell, overlapping activities, unavailability of electricity, lack of learning resources, and non-adherence to policies and guidelines, etc. The schedule of the SLAC is the topmost challenge experienced by them since the planned and original schedule could not be followed due to several activities conducted by DepEd. This challenge has something to do with the difficulty experienced by the teachers (Vega, 2020). With the scheduling of the SLAC session, classes are affected and disrupted. For instance, although the availability of the teacher is considered in scheduling, there are times when the time duration of the SLAC may have exceeded its original time allotment. Additionally, even school heads were really faced with challenges in scheduling because workloads and other tasks of teachers are to be considered (Cortejo, 2022).

Results also showed that funding and financial resources are a challenge since many participants stated that they do not gain financial support in implementing the SLAC session. The School Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) can support the funding, but according to a department head, it requires time since it is a lengthy process (Dilay & Ramos, 2024). Despite the meticulous planning, a project such as SLAC cannot be implemented well without a stable source of funding.

Also, it was revealed that there was no existing model for priority topics in the SLAC session, and some participants found other topics irrelevant. Culajara (2023) stated that there is a lack of needs assessment that may have something to do with the lack of priority topics as previously stated. Supposedly, SLAC is designed to hone the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of the teachers for improved teaching and learning and address the challenges faced by them, but according to some of the participants, the discussed topics were repeated, not filtered, and do not refer to the teachers' needs. De Vera et al. (2020) added that there is no definite evaluation or assessment to check the weak and strong points of the SLAC session and monitor the quality of the services offered by this program. To assess if the action cell is really effective, a concrete evaluation must be done.

These obstacles can hinder the effective execution of SLAC sessions, underscoring the need to examine their views and experiences to identify practical solutions. Given their pivotal role in enhancing teacher capacity, understanding the views and experiences of selected master teachers who are at the forefront of SLAC implementation is also crucial for improving the program's efficacy. There are certain restrictions on the use of SLACs. Vera et al. (2020) enumerated various issues faced by SLACs, such as different and inconsistent scheduling of sessions, disruption of classes, absence of tools for evaluation, and absence of an SLAC model as a guide in the implementation. Cardenas et al. (2023) added that there are some teachers who are not aware of and oriented on the program and are reluctant to engage in SLAC sessions. There were also concerns about the actual topics that should be the focus of the discussion (Vera et al., 2020).

Exploring how master teachers overcome these barriers can provide valuable lessons for improving the sustainability and effectiveness of SLACs. Additionally, SLACs align with DepEd's broader goals of enhancing teacher quality and promoting lifelong learning. This study therefore aimed to provide a guide for successful implementation by documenting the master teachers' practices that support SLAC's effectiveness and the difficulties that they encounter. The literatures currently in publication frequently concentrates on the theoretical foundations and advantages of SLACs, but hardly ever explored the real-life experiences of individuals entrusted with leading these sessions (Amarillo, 2020). The study intends to close the gap between theory and reality by documenting these experiences and offering practical suggestions for improving SLAC programs.

Discovering the creative approaches that master teachers use to conduct SLACs is another goal of the study. These methods, which are frequently unrecorded, will make significant contributions to professional growth and can be used as guidelines by other educators (Garcia & Torres, 2021). Gaining an understanding of these approaches will improve the discussion about teacher-led projects in the Philippine educational system. Furthermore, deeper structural problems in the education sector, like resource allocation and policy support, are reflected in the difficulties master teachers have when implementing SLAC. The study adds to continuing discussions about how to improve the fundamental components of the educational system by bringing attention to these issues (Sarmiento & Asuncion, 2020).

A distinctive setting for researching SLAC implementation is provided by Quezon Province. Its varied educational environments necessitate suited methods for professional growth, offering a chance to study how master teachers handle certain difficulties and modify their methods to suit the demands of both educators and students (Sarmiento & Asuncion, 2020). Practices in other areas with comparable educational environments can benefit from insights gained from this localized setting. This study's importance also goes beyond Quezon Province's divisions as it can generally help the DepEd build policies and programs, especially in improving the planning and execution of professional learning communities nationwide (Dela Cruz & Santos, 2017). This local investigation functions as a microcosm of more general issues and trends in education. Furthermore, the study backs up the objectives of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), which emphasize the importance of professional development and teamwork in achieving teaching quality. By focusing on master teachers' actual experiences, the study contributes to the understanding on how these criteria are operationalized at the local level (DepEd, 2016). This research is relevant and significant since it addresses the changing demands of the Philippine educational system. The information gained from master teachers' practical experiences can be used to create strategies for strengthening SLACs and ensuring that they remain an essential part of school professional development. In order to promote DepEd's mission of providing high-quality, easily accessible, and equitable education for everyone, it aims to use its results to help create professional development programs that are more inclusive and effective.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to explore the views and experiences of selected master teachers in Quezon Province in conducting School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) to identify the best practices, challenges, and opportunities for enhancing teacher professional development and collaboration, ultimately contributing to improved teaching and learning outcomes.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What are the views and experiences of selected master teachers in Quezon Province in conducting School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) as to:
 - 1.1 instructional support;
 - 1.2 curriculum implementation;
 - 1.3 learning delivery;
 - 1.4 professional development; and
 - 1.5 classroom assessment?
2. What challenges do master teachers face in conducting SLACs?

3. How do master teachers address these challenges to ensure the program's success?
4. What opportunities arise for master teachers and their colleagues through the implementation of SLACs?
5. How do the practices and challenges encountered in SLACs influence teacher collaboration, professional growth, and instructional improvements?

Conceptual/Theoretical Framework

The study was grounded on various theories that provide a robust foundation for understanding the practices, challenges, and opportunities associated with SLAC implementation.

Heidegger's and Gadamer's Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. The conceptual basis of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is based on Martin Heidegger's hermeneutic phenomenology, which serves as the study's foundation. According to Heidegger, humans are essentially "Dasein" or beings-in-the-world whose experiences are influenced by their temporal, relational, and contextual existence (Pham, 2022). Heidegger, in contrast to descriptive phenomenology, stresses interpretation as essential to comprehending lived experience, claiming that meaning arises from the interaction between the participant's story and the researcher's interpretive lens (Sumalinog, 2021).

This translates to a twofold hermeneutic in IPA: the participant is making sense of their world as the researcher tries to understand them. The method recognizes that people's experiences are inextricably linked to their cultural, historical, and social contexts (Smith et al., 2021). The analysis is guided by Heidegger's concept of "being-in-the-world," which enables the researcher to investigate how participants derive meaning from their experiences within their lifeworld.

This framework acknowledges that understanding is constantly interpretative, situational, and co-constructed, supporting the study's goal of examining participants' complex, subjective experiences (Smith et al., 2021; Pham, 2022). SLAC sessions are collaborative, context-rich spaces where teachers reflect on practice, share strategies, and co-construct meaning. Heideggerian IPA is well-suited to explore these dynamics because the participant's reflections during SLACs are shaped by their school culture, student needs, and professional relationships, mirroring Heidegger's notion of being-in-the-world. IPA allowed the exploration of how teachers make sense of SLAC experiences, including challenges, growth, and collegiality. SLACs are not just procedural meetings; they are lived, affective experiences that influence identity, pedagogy, and leadership. The study therefore shed light on how SLACs support educators shared meaning, professional development, and accountability, capturing the depth of their reflective journeys, by utilizing Heideggerian IPA.

In addition, Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), theoretically grounded in Hans-Georg Gadamer's hermeneutic philosophy, emphasizes dialogical understanding, historical consciousness, and the fusion of horizons. These concepts are highly relevant to the contemplative and cooperative nature of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions.

Collaborative Professional Learning Theory. The Collaborative Professional Learning Theory by DuFour (2016) as cited in Ikpuri and Peter (2024) is closely aligned with the implementation of School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) in the Philippine education system, particularly in fostering continuous professional development among teachers. Both frameworks emphasize that teacher learning is most effective when done collaboratively, promoting a culture of shared responsibility and mutual support. DuFour advocates that professional learning communities are essential in improving teaching practices and

student outcomes, which resonates with the core purpose of SLACs in providing a venue for teachers to engage in collective discussions on instructional challenges and innovations.

A significant parallel between the two models is the emphasis on collective inquiry and reflective dialogue. Teachers collaborate to address common teaching challenges, share best practices, and find ways to improve instructional delivery during SLAC sessions. This procedure is similar to DuFour's idea of collaborative professional learning, in which teachers have planned discussions with the goal of enhancing their methods. Instead of being passive recipients of training, these cooperative interactions empower teachers to take an active role in their own professional development.

Moreover, the significance of data-driven decision-making and action-oriented learning is emphasized by both DuFour's theory and SLACs. Teachers are encouraged in SLACs to use classroom observations and student performance data to identify learning gaps, create interventions, and assess how well their strategies are effective. DuFour's idea that professional learning communities should concentrate on enhancing student outcomes through evidence-based approaches is in line with this approach.

The Collaborative Professional Learning Theory (CPLT), rooted in Vygotsky's sociocultural learning framework and the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development, provides a strong theoretical foundation for the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) as a school-based professional development strategy in the Philippine education system. CPLT emphasizes that learning is a socially mediated process where individuals construct knowledge through interaction, shared inquiry, and reflective practice. SLAC embodies this theory by facilitating collaborative learning sessions among teachers to address instructional challenges, share best practices, and enhance pedagogical competencies (Sales, 2024).

According to DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016, SLAC is designed to foster communities of practice where teachers engage in ongoing problem-solving, reflective dialogue, and collective action planning. These elements align with Collaborative Professional Learning Theory principles of dialogic and multimodal learning, where collaboration leads to deeper understanding and professional growth (Llego, 2025). Studies have shown that SLAC implementation significantly improves teachers' instructional mastery, pedagogical efficacy, and professional attitudes, especially when supported by effective leadership and structured monitoring and evaluation mechanisms (Gamboa, 2023).

Knowles' Adult Learning Theory. Knowles' Adult Learning Theory as cited in Bouchrika (2024) and often known as andragogy, offers important insights into the features of adult learners and the best strategies to support their learning. The unique needs and traits of adult learners are highlighted by andragogy, in contrast to standard pedagogical approaches, which are intended for children. These include a strong sense of self-direction, the importance placed on past experiences, and a predilection for knowledge that is directly applicable to real-world circumstances. Knowles' ideas are especially applicable to School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) since these programs are created to accommodate these very traits of adult learners, which makes them an appropriate model for teacher professional development (Knowles, 1980; Merriam, 2001).

Knowles' Adult Learning Theory also emphasizes that master teachers are essential in facilitating learning as they act as role models by exemplifying good teaching techniques and motivating educators to consider their own experiences. Master teachers contribute to the development of a culture of shared learning by establishing a cooperative, encouraging atmosphere where all participants are motivated to take charge of their own professional development (De Castro, 2019; Bouchrika, 2025). This strategy ensures that SLACs are relevant, useful, and based on actual classroom challenges, which makes them an ideal framework for teacher professional development that aligns with andragogy's principles (Pappas, 2025).

Schools and universities frequently employ pedagogy, which assumes that students are passive and in need of teaching. On the contrary, Malcolm Knowles, whose theory is commonly referred to as adult

learning theory or andragogy, assumes that students are self-directed and actively participate in their education. It has been suggested that andragogy is a ‘badge of identity’ or an ‘article of faith’ for many adult educators. In general, when adults enter a learning environment, they have a wider range and depth of life experiences. As a result, learning can be aided when the instruction is connected to these experiences. When attending a workshop that focuses on a particular skill or collection of problems, most adults have precise, short-term goals and are not patient with the facilitator’s interpretation of what is “important for them to learn” (Livingston & Hostos, 2023).

Hence, this study analyzed the beliefs and values underlying these approaches and how they impact the educational experiences of both teachers and students. The ultimate goal is to gain a better understanding of the philosophical basis of these approaches and their potential impact on the future of education. Adult learning theory informs teaching methodology developed to focus more on learner-based practices that grow from the content of lessons.

Knowles’s Adult Learning Theory provides a powerful theoretical lens for understanding the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) as a professional development strategy in the Philippine education system. Knowles posited that adult learners are self-directed, bring a wealth of experience to the learning process, are ready to learn when they perceive a need, and are motivated by internal factors such as job satisfaction and personal growth. These principles align closely with the structure and goals of SLAC, which is designed to foster collaborative, reflective, and context-based learning among teachers.

In SLAC sessions, teachers engage in peer-led discussions, action planning, and problem-solving activities that are directly relevant to their classroom experiences. This relevance is critical, as Knowles emphasized that adult learners need to see the immediate applicability of what they are learning to their professional roles. Moreover, SLAC encourages experiential learning and reflection, both of which are central to Knowles’ model. Teachers are not passive recipients of information but active participants who co-construct knowledge through dialogue and shared practice, embodying the andragogical principle of learner involvement in the planning and evaluation of their learning.

Thus, integrating Knowles’s Adult Learning Theory into the theoretical framework of SLAC not only validates its design but also strengthens its potential as a transformative tool for teacher development. It ensures that professional learning is not only sustained and collaborative but also responsive to the unique characteristics and motivations of adult educators.

Wenger’s Communities of Practice. Wenger’s Communities of Practice (1998) theory, as cited in Wenger-Trayner (2015), offers a compelling paradigm for understanding how learning takes place among people who have similar interests and objectives. Wenger asserts that learning is a social process that is influenced by interactions within a society rather than only being an individual activity. This idea is especially relevant to School Learning Action Cells (SLACs), where educators gather with the common goal of advancing student learning and teaching methods. The emphasis of SLACs is on collaborative learning, when teachers share experiences, exchange discussions, and work together to solve problems to learn from one another. This supports Wenger’s theory that when people with similar interests regularly connect to create and improve shared practices, a community of practice is created (Wenger-Trayner, 2015).

Master teachers facilitate these communities of practice within the framework of SLACs. They guide the conversations, promote idea sharing, and make sure the community stays committed to its objective of enhancing instructional strategies. In their capacity as facilitators, master teachers set an example of successful teaching techniques, promote reflection, and offer an opportunity for teacher collaboration. Teachers can exchange best practices, difficulties, and insights in a dynamic learning environment created by this facilitation (Prudente et al., 2024; Dumandan, 2025). Wenger’s idea of a community of practice is characterized by the sense of belonging and support that SLACs provide for

teachers over time. Teachers develop a supportive professional network that fosters their growth as a group by depending on one another for guidance, critiques, and encouragement (ASEAN Secretariat, 2025).

The Community of Practice (CoP) theory provides a compelling framework for understanding the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) as a collaborative and context-driven professional development model in the Philippine education system. As mentioned earlier, community of practice is a group of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis (Wenger et al., 2002 as cited in Aclan & Ching, 2022). This theoretical lens aligns closely with the structure and goals of SLAC, which fosters sustained collaboration among teachers to improve instructional practices and student outcomes.

SLAC sessions are designed to promote shared learning through reflective dialogue, collaborative planning, and problem-solving which are core elements of a functioning Community of Practice. According to Aclan and Ching (2022), teachers participating in SLACs reported high levels of engagement in collaborative activities such as lesson planning, curriculum contextualization, and action implementation, all of which contributed to improved teaching performance. Similarly, De Guzman et al. (2023) emphasized that SLACs serve as school-based communities of practice that support continuous professional development through the sharing of best practices and peer mentoring.

Burns' Transformational Leadership Theory. Transformational leadership which is defined as a sense of autonomy and responsibility can increase engagement and output (Dukhaykh et al., 2024). Work engagement can be viewed as an active state of well-being and is demonstrated by vigor, dedication, and involvement at work. High levels of employee well-being at work have the greatest potential to benefit both workers and organizations. Active and receptive to new information, engaged employees are fully committed to their tasks and delivering excellent results.

In SLACs, master teachers play a crucial role in motivating their peers to engage in reflective practice and adopt new, evidence-based teaching practices. By creating an environment that encourages open communication, collaboration, and critical thinking, master teachers model the behaviors they wish to inspire in their colleagues. They provide guidance on best practices, encourage teachers to share their classroom experiences, and help their peers navigate the challenges they face in the classroom. This process of empowerment is a key aspect of transformational leadership as it enables teachers to develop confidence in their abilities, take ownership of their professional growth, and contribute to the improvement of the educational community (Baldera, 2025; Sumampong & Arnado, 2024; Meidelina et al., 2023; Koci, 2025).

Together, these theories provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the dynamics of SLACs and the pivotal role of master teachers. By integrating insights from these theoretical perspectives, the study aimed to shed light on how SLACs contribute to professional development, foster collaboration, and address the challenges and opportunities faced by educators in three school divisions of Quezon Province.

Conceptual/Theoretical Paradigm

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

The views and experiences of selected master teachers encompass the personal and subjective encounters they have when participating in or leading School Learning Action Cells (SLACs). These experiences are shaped by their feelings, reflections, and perceptions about the SLAC activities. The study sought to delve deeply into how master teachers experience these professional development sessions—what they find meaningful, how they perceive the relevance of the content, and how these experiences influence their teaching practices and overall professional identity. This exploration aimed to capture the essence of their involvement and understand the value they place on SLACs as part of their career journey.

Perceived benefits of SLACs refer to the positive outcomes that master teachers believe they gain through their participation in these professional development activities. These advantages may be both personal and professional, such as improved classroom management skills and exposure to innovative teaching approaches. Teachers may also find personal fulfillment in having the opportunity to collaborate with colleagues and advance their careers.

The different techniques, approaches, and strategies that master teachers use in the classroom are reflected in their teaching practices; many of them may have been influenced by their involvement in SLACs. These approaches which encourage student participation and improve learning results may involve innovative teaching strategies, interactive learning strategies, and cooperative learning approaches. Master teachers may enhance their current methods or implement innovative strategies that promote a more dynamic and efficient learning environment through SLACs. Examining these practices helps to understand the direct influence of SLACs on how teachers design and implement lessons.

Instructional improvement refers to the enhancements in the quality and effectiveness of teaching as a result of participating in SLACs. To better meet the needs of their students, master teachers may

implement new teaching strategies, enhance their lesson planning, and improve their teaching pedagogies as they gain new knowledge and abilities through SLAC activities. This development enhances the overall quality of education in their institutions in addition to influencing their specific teaching philosophies. Better student involvement, better assessment, and an overall improvement in student learning outcomes could all be signs of a positive impact on student learning outcomes.

Through SLACs, master teachers and their colleagues are presented with various professional opportunities. These can include exposure to new teaching strategies, the chance to collaborate with peers from different schools, and opportunities to take on leadership roles in educational initiatives. A collaborative learning environment is often created by SLACs so that teachers can share experiences, share ideas, and gain knowledge from one another. In addition to empowering individual educators, this collaborative approach encourages a culture of lifelong learning among the larger teaching community. Master teachers can expand their professional networks and acquire skills that advance their careers by engaging in one of these opportunities.

Teacher collaboration and professional growth go together within the context of SLACs. Master teachers share information and instructional techniques with their colleagues as they work together, fostering collaborative learning and professional growth. Teachers feel more connected to one another because of this collaboration, which enables them to support one another in challenges. Teachers benefit from this collaboration throughout time as they get new perspectives on pedagogical approaches, educational trends, and instructional practices. In the end, collaboration improves the teaching and learning environment, which benefits both teachers and students.

While SLACs offer many benefits, master teachers also face various challenges in their implementation. A colleague's resistance to change, a lack of resources or support, and logistical problems like scheduling time for SLAC sessions can all be instances of these challenges. Furthermore, organizational or contextual constraints may make it difficult for certain teachers to implement new techniques they have learned in SLACs in their classrooms. By addressing these issues, SLAC may be improved upon and delivered, maintaining its efficacy and accessibility for all teachers. By addressing these issues, a more encouraging atmosphere for professional growth will be established.

Based on the experiences, challenges, and perceived benefits expressed by master teachers, a policy brief in facilitating school learning action cells for enhancing SLACs was made. This policy brief can help improve the facilitation of school learning action cells and ultimately contribute to improved educational outcomes.

Each of these concepts plays a crucial role in understanding the multifaceted impact of SLACs on master teachers and their teaching practices. Exploring these aspects could provide valuable insights into how SLACs shape the professional development of teachers and the overall quality of education in the three school divisions of Quezon Province.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted a qualitative research design with interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) approach to explore the views and experiences of master teachers in the three school divisions of Quezon Province, namely the Quezon Province Schools Division, the Lucena City Schools Division, the Tayabas City Schools Division, in conducting School Learning Action Cells (SLACs). This type of research investigates views and experiences to better understand how people interpret those experiences, grasp how

humans think, and broaden a researcher's perspective of a topic (Adeniran et al., 2024). It is appropriate for the present study as it focused on documenting subjective experiences and viewpoints of master teachers, giving the researcher a comprehensive grasp of the opportunities, difficulties, and challenges related to SLAC implementation. The study also aimed to understand the core of master teachers' roles in promoting teacher cooperation and professional development by exploring their personal narratives. A policy brief was then developed as an output to effectively facilitate school learning action cells.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the three school divisions of Quezon Province: the Quezon Province Schools Division, the Lucena City Schools Division, and the Tayabas City Schools Division.

The three schools divisions of Quezon Province are known for their strong emphasis on educational development and their commitment to implementing programs that enhance teaching quality and student learning outcomes. They were selected as the research locale due to their active implementation of School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) as part of their professional development initiatives. SLACs are widely recognized in the division as a collaborative platform for teacher training and instructional improvement, making it an ideal setting to explore the views and experiences of selected master teachers who play a central role in facilitating these sessions.

The communities served by the divisions' schools were varied and included both urban and rural places. Because of this diversity, the study was able to record a broad range of viewpoints on the application of SLAC, representing the particular opportunities and difficulties faced by master teachers in various educational settings. The study intended to offer contextually grounded and relevant insights into the realities of the local educational system by placing the research in Quezon Province.

Through its focus on this locale, the study aimed to contribute to the understanding of how SLACs were operationalized in the context of Quezon Province, providing valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and other stakeholders involved in promoting teacher collaboration and professional growth.

Research Population and Sample

This study employed a purposive sampling design to select participants who could provide in-depth insights into the views and experiences of selected master teachers in conducting School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) within Quezon Province; namely the Quezon Province Schools Division, the Lucena City Schools Division, and the Tayabas City Schools Division.

Purposive sampling was used to carefully select master teachers who take an active role in SLAC activities at their schools and divisions. By ensuring that the participants have firsthand knowledge of the phenomenon under investigation, this approach enabled a thorough examination of their viewpoints and perspectives. The study could offer a thorough grasp of the crucial responsibilities master teachers play in SLAC implementation and the program's influence on the professional development of teachers in the three school divisions.

The criteria for participant selection included the following:

1. master teachers currently employed in the three Schools Division of Quezon Province;
2. with active involvement in the planning, facilitation, or implementation of SLACs;

3. with at least one year of experience facilitating SLACs to ensure they have sufficient exposure to its processes and challenges.

To gather a list of suitable master teachers who meet the criteria, the sampling procedure commenced at the Schools Division Offices of Quezon Province, Lucena City, and Tayabas City. After that, the researcher humbly extended an invitation to possible participants via official means, such as emails or letters, outlining the goals, parameters, and ethical issues of the study. To verify their voluntary participation, those who agreed to participate were required to sign an informed consent form.

Given the qualitative nature of the study, the sample size was limited to 15 participants: 5 from SDO Quezon Province, 5 from SDO Lucena, and 5 from SDO Tayabas. This method contributed to a comprehensive view of the program's effects by enabling a comprehensive understanding of SLAC implementation in various school environments. After selecting the co-researchers, the researcher prepared all communications and sought permission to conduct an individual interview with the teachers.

Data Gathering Procedure

A semi-structured interview guide designed to elicit thorough responses from the participants served as the main research tool for this study. To encourage master teachers to share their experiences, practices, difficulties, and ideas regarding organizing and conducting SLACs, the guide contained open-ended questions. With this method, interviews can be flexible, allowing participants to give comprehensive responses while also allowing the researcher to delve deeper into relevant subjects. The researcher-made interview guide was validated by the expertise of five validators to ensure the relevance of the questions in eliciting data from the co-researchers. The validators were composed of an assistant school principal, a Master Teacher II, and three with Teacher III rank. All of them have their respective doctorate degrees and are considered experts in the field.

The master teachers who have actively participated in SLAC implementation were purposively selected after obtaining permission from the Quezon Province, Lucena City, and Tayabas City Schools Division Offices to conduct the study. In each school division, there were five master teachers. Participants were briefed on the study's objectives and procedures, and informed consent were obtained to ensure ethical compliance. This initial phase set the stage for a thorough exploration of the research questions while ensuring that ethical considerations were met.

After that, in-depth interviews with each master teacher were conducted utilizing the semi-structured guide. To ensure that participants feel comfortable discussing their experiences, these interviews were placed in a setting that promoted honest and open communication. With their permission, notetaking was done to document nonverbal clues in addition to context and interviews were audio recorded to ensure accuracy.

Individual interviews started with a short prayer followed by the introduction of the researcher and presentation of the research rationale. The researcher requested permission from the co-researcher to record the interview to collect all useful information in developing the policy brief for facilitating the school learning action cell.

On the other hand, the researcher, as the interviewer, initiated and drove the interview path to come up with a more comprehensive and better saturation of the responses. The researcher interviewed the co-researchers at the time of their availability at the end of every class. All the proceedings were audio recorded via phone with the consent of all the co-researchers. The recordings were transcribed manually. After which, their responses during the interview were presented back to them to clarify if the transcription made were

congruent to their answers. Each interview lasted for 45 to 60 minutes. Data saturation was reached when the co-researchers were able to repeat the same concept and no new ideas were gathered.

Finally, relevant documents such as SLAC plans, session feedback, and reports were reviewed to analyze the findings from the interviews. Using thematic analysis, the gathered data were transcribed, organized, and analyzed. The process entailed getting familiar with the data, creating initial codes, identifying themes, and synthesizing the results into an organized narrative. This study ensured a thorough examination of the views and experiences of selected master teachers by integrating various data sources and analysis methodologies, offering insightful analysis and practical recommendations for enhancing SLAC implementation.

Data Analysis

This study employed an interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) to systematically explore the views and experiences of selected master teachers in conducting School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) in the three Schools Divisions of Quezon Province. This approach allowed for a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of how participants make sense of their roles, challenges, and contributions within the SLAC framework. By using IPA, the study explored the master teachers' subjective interpretations and personal reflections, providing profound insights into their professional experiences.

Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) by Smith et al. (2021) is a well-established qualitative approach developed to investigate individuals' views and experiences. It is concerned with the particular experiences that individuals have and their meaning-making that occurs in relation to those experiences (Smith & Fieldsend, 2021).

The data collection process involved in-depth interviews to capture diverse perspectives and analyze findings. IPA guided the analysis by focusing on the participants' view and experiences, emphasizing both what they described and how they interpreted those experiences. This dual-layered approach ensured that the voices of the participants were central to the study while allowing for the researcher's interpretative lens to uncover deeper meanings. This study followed the seven-step process of IPA to ensure depth, transparency, and interpretative integrity.

The first stage of the analysis involved familiarizing oneself with the data known as reading and re-reading. Interview transcriptions were meticulously prepared and carefully examined to ensure that the participants' experiences are fully grasped. Reading these transcripts again helped in identifying initial patterns and emotional expressions, and comprehensive notes were written to document significant findings that support the research objectives. The objective of this phase was to take the participants' accounts of their experiences. Familiarizing with the data by rereading the passages or data from the interview with the master teachers would be necessary to build the ideas. Transcripts were read multiple times to absorb emotional tone, contextual nuances, and significant expressions.

Next step was initial noting. The data underwent systematic coding to break down the narratives into smaller units of meaning. A systematic breakdown of narrative into smaller units to dissect the thoughts from master teachers was crucial. Segments of text that provide meaningful insights into the practices, challenges, and opportunities related to SLACs were identified and categorized. In accordance with the IPA methodology, the coding process concentrated on documenting participants' views, feelings, and interpretations. To ensure consistency and conformity with the objectives of the study, a coding framework was created. Detailed exploratory comments were written in the margins of the transcripts focusing on the descriptive, linguistic, and conceptual comments.

Third step was developing emergent themes. Once the coding process was completed, emerging themes were identified. These themes represented recurring ideas and patterns that reflect key aspects of the participants' experiences, such as effective planning and facilitation practices, strategies for overcoming challenges, and the perceived benefits of SLACs. The researcher engaged in an interpretative process, linking individual accounts to broader thematic structures that convey shared meanings across participants.

Searching for connections across emergent themes followed. Themes then underwent a process of review and refinement. They were checked for relevance to the research questions and supported by adequate data. Underdeveloped concepts were improved upon or eliminated, while repetitive or overlapping themes were combined. To enhance the credibility of the findings, the themes were validated through member checking, where participants review preliminary interpretations and peer debriefing, where experts provide feedback on the analytical process. This is also known as theme clustering.

After each participant, analysis moved to the next case. This is relevant to treat each participant independently and to maintain the unique perspective of each co-researcher before integrating cross-case insights.

After doing the different steps, the next step was looking for patterns across cases. Patterns were identified across the dataset. Convergences and divergences were noted, highlighting common challenges and shared successes about SLACs implementation.

The final stage involved synthesizing the findings into a detailed narrative that highlights the views and experiences of selected master teachers in SLAC implementation. Direct quotes were included to illustrate participants' voices authentically, while the interpretative layer offered insights into the meanings behind their experiences. Synthesis was employed to compare data from interviews and document reviews, strengthening the reliability and validity of the results.

Figure 2. Seven Steps of Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

Specialist Informants

For the accuracy of the study's results, specialist informants validated the results. Their result validation aided the researcher in developing a policy brief for conducting learning action cells. The following are the qualifications of the specialist informants:

1. must have graduated with a doctorate degree;
2. have specialized in qualitative research;
3. have an in-depth knowledge of the SLAC.

In this study, five specialist informants thoroughly validated the results. They were composed of two education program supervisors, a Principal III, a Master Teacher, and a Vice President for Academics. All of them have a deep understanding on the implementation of SLAC program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the data gathered, the following findings are derived:

Views and Experiences of Selected Master Teachers in Quezon Province in Conducting School Learning Action Cell as to Instructional Support

From an experiential standpoint, the master teachers' narratives revealed rich and detailed accounts of their roles in planning, facilitating, and evaluating SLAC sessions. Their views and experiences demonstrated how instructional support was grounded in real classroom needs, peer collaboration, and the actual context of their schools. In terms of behavioral evidence, the master teachers described observable practices such as conducting pre- and post-tests, crafting instructional materials, facilitating professional development workshops, and engaging in coaching and mentoring. These concrete actions confirmed that SLACs were not only conceptual discussions but were also actively implemented through structured and intentional strategies. From a reflective lens, the master teachers conveyed their own growth and transformation. They reflected on past challenges, such as rigid facilitation styles or multiple role demands, and how these experiences informed their current practices. They expressed a strong sense of purpose and commitment to supporting their fellow teachers, which demonstrated a deep internalization of their leadership role. The convergence of these three dimensions—experience, behavior, and reflection—strengthens the credibility and trustworthiness of the findings, confirming that SLACs serve as meaningful, data-informed, and empowering mechanisms of instructional support in the views and experiences of selected master teachers in Quezon Province.

The views and experiences of master teachers in Quezon Province highlight SLACs as crucial platforms for instructional support. These sessions are collaborative, data-informed, and empowering, grounded in shared expertise and reflective dialogue. Despite challenges, master teachers sustain their commitment to guiding peers in improving instructional quality for enhanced student outcomes. Their experiences validate the role of teacher leadership in building school-based professional learning communities.

Views and Experiences of Selected Master Teachers in Quezon Province in Conducting School Learning Action Cell as to Curriculum Implementation

Master teachers shared how SLAC planning began with a review of the curriculum guide, analysis of learner data, and collaboration with school heads and department chairs. These accounts were grounded in real practice, such as the integration of the MATATAG curriculum and alignment with IPCRF outputs. Behaviorally, master teachers described routine practices such as identifying underperforming competencies, designing responsive activities, and conducting follow-up monitoring to evaluate application. These actions demonstrate that curriculum implementation was a sustained and interactive process. Finally, the reflective dimension emerged in how master teachers revised SLAC topics, adapted to new reforms, and learned from previous facilitation experiences. The intersection of these three dimensions confirms that SLACs are not only vehicles for teacher training but are embedded in the larger process of instructional planning, curriculum execution, and learning recovery.

Views and Experiences of Selected Master Teachers in Quezon Province in Conducting School Learning Action Cell as to Learning Delivery

From the experiential perspective, master teachers narrated a variety of strategies they used in real settings, including group activities, hands-on creation of instructional materials, and use of lesson exemplars. These firsthand experiences reflect a grounded understanding of learning facilitation. In terms of behavioral evidence, the use of collaborative tools like brainstorming, active learning strategies like think-pair-share and structured activities demonstrate intentional planning and consistent engagement. Meanwhile, the reflective dimension is evident in how they assess the effectiveness of their facilitation by inviting teacher feedback, promoting self-reflection, and adapting to the evolving needs of participants. Together, these three dimensions confirm that the master teachers' strategies in delivering learning through SLACs are holistic, evidence-informed, and grounded in both best practices and responsiveness to local teaching realities.

Views and Experiences of Selected Master Teachers in Quezon Province in Conducting School Learning Action Cell as to Professional Development

From an experiential perspective, teachers recounted real strategies used to integrate professional development, such as needs assessment, inviting resource persons, and aligning SLACs with RPMS-PPST indicators. These grounded actions reflect intentional integration of Professional Development into SLAC design. The master teachers also stated that mentorship, coaching, group outputs (e.g., action research), and reflective tools (e.g., learning logs, self-assessment) foster professional growth. SLACs helped teachers recognize their strengths, rethink their practices, and build supportive learning communities. The convergence of these three dimensions confirms that SLACs are not only operationally useful, but deeply transformational, enabling both instructional excellence and personal development among teachers in the province.

Views and Experiences of Selected Master Teachers in Quezon Province in Conducting School Learning Action Cell as to Classroom Assessment

The integration of classroom assessment into SLAC sessions is well-supported. Experientially, master teachers described real-life practices such as test construction workshops, analysis of summative results, and group evaluation of learning outcomes. They also shared concrete actions like preparing rubrics, conducting MPS analysis, and requiring post-SLAC application tasks. These show that classroom assessment is not just discussed but actively practiced and refined. From a reflective lens, master teachers highlighted how student performance served as feedback on their teaching strategies, encouraging them to redesign instruction for better outcomes. Collectively, these layers confirm that SLACs are effective platforms for strengthening teachers' assessment literacy and for aligning classroom assessments with instruction and student learning goals.

Challenges of Master Teachers in Conducting SLACs

Experientially, the co-researchers cited real obstacles such as scheduling conflicts, teacher burnout, and lack of instructional resources. These firsthand accounts reveal the systemic pressures placed on SLAC facilitators. Behaviorally, teachers' low attendance, distraction during sessions, and failure to submit outputs on time indicate a disconnect between the intended outcomes of SLACs and actual teacher engagement. From a reflective lens, master teachers expressed emotional strain, but many maintained a positive attitude

by adjusting facilitation strategies and practicing empathy to re-engage their peers. The convergence of these themes demonstrates that SLAC implementation, while valuable, is fraught with logistical, emotional, and institutional challenges. Addressing these requires supportive leadership, adequate resources, teacher empowerment, and structured planning to sustain meaningful teacher development.

Coping Strategies of Master Teachers to Address Challenges

The responses of the master teachers revealed that managing the challenges associated with SLAC (School Learning Action Cell) implementation required adaptive, collaborative, and data-informed coping strategies. These included intentional planning, flexible scheduling, feedback and Evaluation Practices Helped Teachers Assess SLAC Effectiveness, Clear Role Distribution, Reliable Feedback Systems, Teacher Empowerment, and deep understanding of peer needs.

Professional Opportunities for Master Teachers and Colleagues through the Implementation of SLACs

SLACs provide multifaceted opportunities for Master Teachers and their colleagues. These include enhancement of leadership capabilities, creation of strong professional networks, reflective and continuous learning, and tangible benefits such as career progression and improved instructional practices.

Influence of Practices and Challenges of SLACs among Teachers

The master teachers' perspectives in this study confirm that SLACs have a significant impact on three main areas: promoting collaborative culture, nurturing professional growth, and enhancing instructional delivery. These effects are not independent but rather interconnected. Collaboration fosters growth, growth enables innovation, and innovation circles back to benefit both peers and students.

Synthesis

In order to support teachers' ongoing professional development through collaborative sessions, School Learning Action Cells have been adopted in all Philippine schools, especially public schools. SLAC has advantages and disadvantages, making it easier said than done. Instructional assistance for grassroots SLAC implementation is investigated in this study. Teachers typically benefit from collaborative sharing of teaching resources and best practices. Aligning the SLAC implementation can be achieved by concentrating on the planning needs that are backed by the provided data. Additionally, teachers may benefit from professional development via coaching and mentorship, as well as empowerment and inclusive engagement. Despite the difficulties, a strong commitment to the program's support is also required in properly implementing SLACs.

SLACs are dynamic platforms for improving teaching and learning, according to master teachers in Quezon Province. In order to enhance classroom practices, master teachers provided systematic mentoring, lesson planning, and observation feedback to their colleagues. In order to ensure consistency and relevance in instruction, teaching practices were aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) through the use of SLAC sessions. Teachers investigated a variety of engaging pedagogical strategies for learning delivery that were appropriate for the circumstances of their students. Additionally, SLACs offered teachers significant chances for professional growth through capacity-building, reflective discussion, and collaborative knowledge sharing. Regarding assessment in the

classroom, master teachers led conversations and activities regarding the creation and evaluation of formative and summative tests that were in line with students' skills and curricular requirements.

When implementing SLAC, master teachers in Quezon Province encountered a number of difficulties. These included practical issues like time restraints, conflicting duties, restricted resource availability, and varying degrees of teachers' participation. Maintaining engagement, meeting various learning needs, and making sure that teaching strategies and approaches learned in SLACs were applied beyond session. Master teachers continued to provide meaningful sessions despite these limitations. These difficulties highlight how crucial it is to offer administrative support, capacity-building, and structural support to enable SLACs in the province to reach their full potential.

Meanwhile, to guarantee the success of SLACs, master teachers in Quezon Province implemented proactive coping measures. These included peer-led facilitation, digital integration, resource mobilization, flexible scheduling, and cooperative planning. SLACs were customized to meet the needs of both teachers and students through the use of reflective practices, output-based standards, and data-driven decision-making. Encouraging teacher participation also required a supportive climate, motivating strategies, and coordination with school administrators. These flexible solutions demonstrate master teachers' adaptability and leadership potential in negotiating the challenging realities of school-based professional development.

For master teachers and their peers, School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) offered substantial professional view. SLACs promoted leadership development, improved reflective practice, encouraged teamwork in professional development, supported ongoing education, and aided in career promotion and recognition. All things considered, SLACs provided a vibrant setting for enhancing teaching potential, boosting professional self-assurance, and fostering an excellence culture in educational institutions.

Teacher collaboration, professional development, and instructional progress were greatly impacted by SLAC procedures and the difficulties faced in Quezon Province. Master teachers and their colleagues created a professional culture rooted in ongoing learning via shared leadership and accountability. SLACs encouraged reflective practice, fostered collegial discourse, and helped teachers improve the way they delivered their lessons. These results enhanced instructors' individual proficiency as well as the overall growth of school communities, resulting in more adaptable and efficient teaching-learning procedures throughout the province.

Eidetic Insights

Figure 3. Symbolic Representation of the Views and Experiences of Selected Master Teachers in Conducting SLACs

After reflecting deeply on the experiences shared by my co-researchers, I found that the image of a river always flowing, strong, and full of life perfectly represents their journey as master teachers. I chose the symbol of running water to show how master teachers continue to facilitate in School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions, even when faced with many challenges in their daily work.

Master teachers are also classroom teachers who carry heavy responsibilities every day. Despite this, they still manage to conduct and attend SLAC sessions as required by the Department of Education. While some may facilitate these sessions simply to comply with the DepEd Order, their consistent involvement shows a deeper commitment to learning and working together. No matter how busy or tired they are, master teachers remain dedicated to their duties and continue to support each other.

The river symbolizes three important lessons from their experiences. First, flexibility is a defining trait of master teachers. Much like water that flows around obstacles and adapts to its environment, master teachers demonstrate flexibility in various ways. For instance, they readily adjust SLAC (School Learning Action Cell) schedules when conflicts arise due to other school activities that teachers must attend. They also adapt their instructional tools shifting from digital presentations using LCD projectors to traditional materials like manila paper when technology is unavailable. This responsiveness stems from their awareness that many teachers are visual learners who benefit from concrete visuals to reinforce understanding, rather than relying solely on verbal discussion.

Moreover, master teachers employ diverse strategies and approaches to make SLAC sessions engaging and interactive, ensuring that professional development remains meaningful. They even manage to facilitate these sessions while simultaneously completing classroom-related tasks such as preparing school forms since the master teachers are also classroom teachers. Despite multiple responsibilities, master teachers consistently find ways to adjust, respond to challenges, and keep moving forward with purpose and dedication.

Second is sustenance and renewal. Just as running water sustains life, continuous learning empowers master teachers. Within the classroom, they gain insights from their students' diverse experiences and perspectives. During SLAC sessions, they engage in collaborative learning with colleagues sharing strategies, reflecting on practices, and exchanging ideas. These moments of professional dialogue not only deepen their understanding but also renew their motivation, even amidst demanding workloads. Their passion for teaching fuels their commitment to growth. After each SLAC session, master teachers carry the collective wisdom back to their classrooms and personal lives, applying what they have learned to enrich teaching and strengthen their professional practice.

Third is continuous existence. The river never stops flowing, just like the cycle of learning in SLAC. Even if the topics discussed are familiar, learned in college, graduate school, or past seminars, master teachers still find value in revisiting them. Often, these topics are updated to match new policies or teaching methods that need to be disseminated to teachers. This shows that learning is a lifelong process, and they are always open to growth.

In the end, the river is a powerful symbol of what it means to be a master teacher. It reflects their strength, flexibility, and commitment to learning. Through SLAC, master teachers continue to grow together with their colleagues and learners, proving that even in the face of challenges, they remain true to their duty as master teachers in conducting SLAC's.

Conclusions

Based on the results and discussion, the following conclusions are derived:

1. Selected master teachers in Quezon Province revealed that SLACs serve as dynamic platforms for enhancing teaching and learning. As to instructional support, master teachers guided their colleagues through structured mentoring, lesson planning, and observation feedback to improve classroom practices. Regarding curriculum implementation, SLAC sessions were utilized to align teaching strategies with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), ensuring consistency and relevance in instruction. For learning delivery, teachers explored a range of engaging pedagogical approaches suited to their learners' contexts. SLACs also provided meaningful opportunities for professional development where teachers engaged in capacity-building, reflective dialogue, and collaborative knowledge exchange. In terms of classroom assessment, master teachers facilitated discussions and practices on the development and analysis of formative and summative assessments aligned with learners' abilities and curriculum standards. These experiences highlight the contextual effectiveness of SLACs in addressing the professional needs of teachers in Quezon Province.
2. Master teachers in Quezon Province faced several challenges in SLAC implementation which included logistical concerns such as time constraints, overlapping responsibilities, limited access to resources, and varied levels of teacher participation. Some encountered difficulties in sustaining engagement, addressing differentiated learning needs, and ensuring application of strategies post-session.
3. Master Teachers in Quezon Province adopted proactive coping strategies to ensure the success of SLACs. These included flexible scheduling, collaborative planning, resource mobilization, digital integration, and peer-led facilitation. Reflective practices, output-based requirements, and data-driven decision-making were used to tailor SLACs to the needs of both teachers and students. Coordination with school heads, motivational approaches, and fostering a supportive environment were also vital in encouraging teacher participation.
4. School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) provided significant professional opportunities for both Master Teachers and their colleagues. SLACs facilitated leadership development, enhanced reflective practice, fostered collaborative professional growth, supported continuous learning, and contributed to career advancement and recognition. Overall, SLACs served as a dynamic platform for strengthening instructional capacity, building professional confidence, and cultivating a culture of excellence within schools.
5. SLAC practices and the challenges encountered in Quezon Province significantly influenced teacher collaboration, professional growth, and instructional improvement. Through shared leadership and mutual accountability, Master Teachers and their peers built a professional culture anchored in continuous learning. SLACs facilitated collegial dialogue, promoted reflective practice, and allowed teachers to refine their instructional delivery. These outcomes contributed not only to the individual competence of teachers but also to the collective development of school communities, leading to more responsive and effective teaching-learning processes in the province.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. To the Schools Division Offices (SDO) in Quezon Province. It is recommended that the SDO institutionalize sustained support for SLAC implementation by providing clear policy guidance, logistical resources, and technical assistance. A designated schedule within the school calendar for SLACs should be established to avoid conflicts with other school activities. Likewise, regular

monitoring and evaluation tools must be enhanced to assess the effectiveness of SLACs in improving instructional quality.

2. To School Heads and Administrators. School leaders may actively support master teachers by ensuring time-bound, uninterrupted SLAC sessions and endorsing their recommendations for school-based improvements. They are also encouraged to allocate sufficient resources and foster a collaborative culture that values peer mentoring, shared leadership, and continuous learning.
3. To Master Teachers. Master Teachers are encouraged to continuously innovate SLAC facilitation by using data-driven approaches, incorporating varied teaching strategies, and integrating technology to enhance engagement. They may strengthen their leadership by fostering inclusive and participatory discussions while maintaining reflective practices that promote instructional excellence and peer growth.
4. To Teachers Participating in SLACs. Teachers must view SLACs not as mere compliance, but as meaningful avenues for professional development. They are encouraged to apply the learnings from each session in their classroom practices and provide honest feedback to improve future SLAC activities. Peer support and sharing of best practices may be cultivated to sustain a culture of collaboration.
5. To Future Researchers. Future studies may explore the long-term impact of SLACs on student performance and learning outcomes across various districts in Quezon Province. Comparative research involving other divisions or regions may also uncover unique practices and policies that can further strengthen the implementation of SLACs nationwide.

REFERENCES

- Aclan, M. G. P., & Ching, D. A. (2022). Community of practice and themes of School Learning Action Cell towards better teachers' performances. *The Research Probe*, 2(2). <https://iiari.org/wp-content/uploads/trp.v2.2.irc22.319.pdf>
- Aldrup, K., Carstensen, B., & Klusmann, U. (2022). Is empathy the key to effective teaching? A systematic review of its association with teacher–student interactions and student outcomes. *Educational Psychology Review*, 34, 1177- 1216. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-021-09649-y>
- Abella, J. L., & Dela Rosa, E. (2023). Digital literacy and digital competence of selected Filipino teachers: Basis for a post-pandemic pedagogy. *International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 4(5), 548-569. <https://doi.org/10.46245/ijorer.v4i5.378>
- Aclan, M. G. P., & Ching, D. A. (2022). Community of practice and themes of School Learning Action Cell towards better teachers' performances. *The Research Probe*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.53378/579363>
- Ahmad, H. (2019). Teacher identity development in professional learning: An overview of theoretical frameworks. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335571670>
- Ajani, O. A. (2023). The role of experiential learning in teachers' professional development for enhanced classroom practices. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*, 12(4), 143–153. <https://doi.org/10.5430/jct.v12n4p143>
- Akomodi, J. O. (2025). In-depth analysis: The importance of instructional leadership in education. *Open Journal of Leadership*, 14(2), 177–193. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojl.2025.142008>
- Almonicar Jr., C. D., & Padasas, R. M. (2022). School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) program: The Batuan District experience. *Psychology and Education: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 6, 1092–1099. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7424147>

- Ampler, F. C., & Guhao, E. S., Jr. (2024). Transformational leadership of school heads, teamwork skills, and teacher empowerment: A path model on organizational commitment among public school teachers. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Educational Research (IJM CER)*, 6(5), 20–41. https://www.ijmcer.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/IJM CER_C06502041.pdf
- Aquino, R. A. (2024). School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) program to TLE teachers across their specialization: Challenges and coping mechanism. *EPR A International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(8), 1–15. <https://eprajournals.com/IJMR/article/13828>
- ASEAN Secretariat. (2025). *ASEAN teacher professional development and mobility: Trend report*. https://asean.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/ASCC-RD_Trend-Report_FoE-15_2025_ASEAN-Teacher-Professional-Development-and-Mobility.pdf
- Baatz, J., & Wirzberger, M. (2025). Resilience as a professional competence: A new way towards healthy teachers? *Educational Studies*, 28(56). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-024-10010-8>
- Baldera, P. R. (2025). Instructional leadership in practice: A qualitative exploration of public elementary master teachers' identity formation and influence in the Philippines. *Educational Process: International Journal*, 18, e2025482. <https://doi.org/10.22521/edupij.2025.18.482>
- Banayo, R., & Dizon, L. (2021). Strengthening school-community partnerships for effective teacher professional development in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Education Studies*, 96(2), 45–58.
- Bardach, L., & Klassen, R. M. (2021). Teacher motivation and student outcomes: Searching for the signal. *Educational Psychologist*, 56(4), 283–297. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2021.1991799>
- Bickmore, K., MacDonald, D., & Manion, C. (2021). Teacher learning through communities of practice: Negotiating identity and meaning in professional development. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 44(1), 1–25. <https://journals.sfu.ca/cje/index.php/cje/article/view/456>
- Bouchrika, I. (2025, September 19). *Adult learning theory for 2025: Methods and techniques of teaching adults*. Research.com. <https://research.com/education/adult-learning-theory>
- Brandenburg, R., Glasswell, K., Jones, M., & Ryan, J. (Eds.). (2017). *Reflective theory and practice in teacher education*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3431-2>
- Bustos, M. T. (2023). Design of a self-care module for school teachers: Its basis and enhancements. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 11(5), 241–257. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-11-5-1>
- Cabral, J. V., & Millando, M. R. (2019). School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions and teachers' professional development in Buhaynasapa National High School. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2M). <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AJMRA/article/view/8463>
- Cagumbay-Kadile, M. (2025). Teacher reflective practices and professional development outcomes in the Division of Panabo City. *EPR A International Journal of Environmental Economics, Commerce and Educational Management*, 12(7). <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra22989>
- Camargo Salamanca, S. L., Parra-Martinez, A., & Chang, A. (2024). The effect of scoring rubrics use on self-efficacy and self-regulation. *Educational Psychology Review*, 36(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-024-09906-w>

- Cano García, E. (2024). Peer feedback for teaching professional development: Conditions for it to take effect. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), Article 2391577. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2391577>
- Capistrano, E. P., & Tamayo, M. A. L. (2025). *Comprehensive literature review of career progression of teachers in the Philippines*. ERIC. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED674461.pdf>
- Caskurlu, S., Yalçın, Y., Hur, J., Shi, H., & Klein, J. D. (2025). Data-driven decision-making in instructional design: Instructional designers' practices and strategies. *TechTrends*, 69, 737–748. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-025-01077-x>
- Centillas, J. A., & Villocino, R. P. (2025). Navigating the experiences on School Learning Action Cell: From the journey of coordinators. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 11(3). https://ijariie.com/AdminUploadPdf/NAVIGATING_THE_EXPERIENCES_ON_SCHOOL_LEARNING_ACTION_CELL_FROM_THE_JOURNEY_OF_COORDINATORS_ijariie26542.pdf
- Cobb, J. (2025, August 21). *What is adult learning theory & how to apply its principles*. Learning Revolution. <https://www.learningrevolution.net/adult-learning-theory/>
- Cornish, L. (2024). Reflective practice and professional development. In L. Cornish (Ed.), *Relearning as reflective practitioners* (pp. 109–128). Springer. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-60211-5_8
- Correos, C. T. C., & Paler, A. A. (2020). Extent of implementation, monitoring and evaluation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) as a cost-effective learning and development strategy for teachers development. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 58(1), 61–76. <https://doi.org/10.47119/IJRP100581820201374>
- Crucillo, J. C. (2023). *SLAC implementation to the teachers' professional upskilling and performance: Basis for crafting action plan*. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378296670_Improving_teachers_professional_development_through_School_Learning_Action_Cell_SLAC/fulltext/65d1fa8201325d4652119bad/Improving-teachers-professional-development-through-School-Learning-Action-Cell-SLAC.pdf
- Culajara, C. J. (2023). Improving teachers' professional development through School Learning Action Cell (SLAC). *Journal of Research, Policy & Practice of Teachers and Teacher Education*, 13(1), 76–88. <https://doi.org/10.37134/jrpptte.vol13.1.6.2023>
- Daniels, Z. (2025). *Transforming the experiential classroom: Innovative teaching for engaged learning*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-88165-7>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., Gardner, M., & Espinoza, D. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED606743.pdf>
- De Castro, R. A. (2019). Growth and challenges of master teachers in the province of Batangas. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 2(2), 1–5. https://ijresm.com/Vol.2_2019/Vol2_Iss2_February_19/IJRESM_V2_I2_12.pdf
- De Guzman, M. L. M., Gabales, B. G., Jr., & Labad, V. S. (2023). Learning Action Cell implementation in the Philippine public schools: A descriptive phenomenological study. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 14(27), 59–66. <https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JEP/article/view/61532>

- Deala, M. S., & Lopez, E. A. (2024). School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) implementation and its impact on the personal and professional development among elementary teachers. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 21(3), 253–265. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12536356>
- Deed, C., Blake, D., Henriksen, J., Mooney, A., Prain, V., Tytler, R., Zitzlaff, T., Edwards, M., Emery, S., Muir, T., Swabey, K., Thomas, D., Farrelly, C., Lovejoy, V., Meyers, N., & Finland, D. (2020). Teacher adaptation to flexible learning environments. *Learning Environments Research*, 23, 153–165. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-019-09302-0\[1\]](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-019-09302-0[1])
- DeLuca, C., LaPointe-McEwan, D., & Luhanga, U. (2016). *Approaches to classroom assessment inventory [Database record]*. APA PsycTests. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t60273-000>
- Department of Education. (2016). *Adoption of the Basic Education Research Agenda (DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016)*. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/DO_s2016_039.pdf
- Department of Education. (2016). *DO 35, s. 2016 – The Learning Action Cell as a K to 12 Basic Education Program school-based continuing professional development strategy for the improvement of teaching and learning*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2016/06/07/do-35-s-2016-the-learning-action-cell-as-a-k-to-12-basic-education-program-school-based-continuing-professional-development-strategy-for-the-improvement-of-teaching-and-learning/>
- Department of Education. (2016). *The Learning Action Cell as a K to 12 Basic Education Program school-based continuing professional development strategy for the improvement of teaching and learning (DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016)*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2016/06/07/do-35-s-2016-the-learning-action-cell-as-a-k-to-12-basic-education-program-school-based-continuing-professional-development-strategy-for-the-improvement-of-teaching-and-learning/>
- Department of Education. (2017). *Research management guidelines (DepEd Order No. 16, s. 2017)*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2017/03/20/do-16-s-2017-research-management-guidelines/>
- Department of Education. (2022). *Guidelines on the conduct of the National Learning and Development Needs Assessment (LDNA) (DepEd Memorandum No. 50, s. 2022)*. <https://depedsaragani.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/DM-090-2025-ONLINE-ORIENTATION-ON-LEARNING-AND-DEVELOPMENT-NEEDS-ASSESSMENT.pdf>
- Department of Education. (2023, February 3). *Multi-year guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System–Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST) (DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2023)*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2023/02/03/february-3-2023-dm-008-s-2023-multi-year-guidelines-on-the-results-based-performance-management-system-philippine-professional-standards-for-teachers/>
- Department of Education. (2024). *Policy guidelines on the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum (DepEd Order No. 010, s. 2024)*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2024/07/23/july-23-2024-do-010-s-2024-policy-guidelines-on-the-implementation-of-the-matatag-curriculum/>
- DepEd Bataan. (2023). *Transformational leadership in Philippine schools: Fostering change and growth*. <https://www.depedbataan.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/TRANSFORMATIONAL-LEADERSHIP-IN-PHILIPPINE-SCHOOLS-FOSTERING-CHANGE-AND-GROWTH.pdf>
- DepEd Click. (2024, January 8). *Topics for LAC session (DepEd)*. <https://www.deped-click.com/2024/01/topics-for-lac-session-deped.html>

- DepEd SDO Dasmariñas. (2024). *Submission of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) implementation plans for SY 2024–2025 (Division Memorandum No. 641, s. 2024)*. <https://www.depeddasma.edu.ph/dm-no-641-s-2024-submission-of-school-learning-action-cell-slac-implementation-plans-for-sy-2024-2025/>
- DepEd SDO Dasmariñas. (2025). *Conduct of Learning Action Cell (LAC) / Collaborative Expertise (CE) sessions as part of the Work Application Plan (WAP) (Division Memorandum No. 430, s. 2025)*. <https://www.depeddasma.edu.ph/dm-no-430-s-2025-conduct-of-learning-action-cell-lac-collaborative-expertise-ce-sessions-as-part-of-the-work-application-plan-wap-for-the-implementation-of-revised-k12-curriculum-phase-2-f/>
- Dixon, J., Resor, J., Holmes, L., Hegde, A. V., Goodell, L. S., Mendez, L. I., McMillan, V. J., & Stage, V. C. (2025). Building professional learning communities in head start: A mixed methods study on what it takes from teachers' perspectives. *International Journal of Early Years Education*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669760.2025.2522894>
- Dixson, D. D., & Worrell, F. C. (2016). Formative and summative assessment in the classroom. *Theory Into Practice*, 55(2), 153–159. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43894028>
- Dojillo Jr., M. E. (2025). *The benefits of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC)*. DepEd Bataan Publications. <https://depedbataan.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/THE-BENEFITS-OF-SCHOOL-LEARNING-ACTION-CELL-SLAC.pdf>
- Dumandan, F. (2025). The relationship of professional learning communities' (PLC) engagement towards teachers' competence. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/392529072>
- Eaker, R., DuFour, R., DuFour, R., Mattos, M., & Muhammad, A. (2021). *Revisiting professional learning communities at work®: Proven insights for sustained, substantive school improvement* (2nd ed.). Solution Tree Press. <https://www.solutiontree.com/revisiting-professional-learning-communities-at-work.html>
- Eastridge, J. A., & Benson, W. L. (2020). Comparing two models of collaborative testing for teaching statistics. *Teaching of Psychology*, 47(1), 68–73. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0098628319888113>
- Eliophotou, M. (2024). Transformational leadership and educational outcomes: A literature review. *Journal of Education, Innovation, and Communication (JEICOM)*, 6(1), 98. <https://doi.org/10.34097/jecom-6-1-6>
- Erfe, K. K. B., & Gallego, M. G. (2025). School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) implementation and its impact on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Contemporary Education, Psychology and Health*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15311347>
- Esogon, S. G. T., & Gumban, J. L. (2024). Transformational leadership of school heads in public elementary schools in Bacolod City, Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 8(3), 3244–3255. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/bcp/journal/v8y2024i3sp3244-3255.html>
- Falloon, G. (2020). From digital literacy to digital competence: The teacher digital competency (TDC) framework. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68, 2449–2472. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09767-4>

- Fernando, H. S. (2023). Peer coaching as a strategy in teaching practice: An action research. *Sri Lanka Journal of Education*, 2(1), 18–30. https://www.academia.edu/130092294/Peer_Coaching_as_a_Strategy_in_Teaching_Practice_An_Action_Research
- Filgona, J., Sakiyo, J., Gwany, D. M., & Okoronka, A. U. (2020). Motivation in learning. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 10(4), 16–37. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2020/v10i430253>
- Floreno, F. C. (2021). School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) among secondary school teachers under new normal. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 21(2), 9–18. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2021/v21i230502>
- Fullan, M. (2021). *Leading in a culture of change: Systems for educational improvement*. Jossey-Bass.
- Gamboa, J. C. (2024). Learning Action Cell in professional development: Teachers' perspective. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(3), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i03.21439>
- Gamboa, M. Q. (2023). Implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and its monitoring & evaluation strategies employed by teachers and school heads in the Division of Occidental Mindoro, Philippines. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(11), 2157–2161. <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V4ISSUE11/IJRPR19331.pdf>
- Garza, R., Ovando, M., & O'Doherty, A. (2016). Aspiring school leaders' perceptions of the walkthrough observations. *International Journal of Educational Leadership Preparation*, 11(1). <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1103597>
- Grape, F. C. (2025). *Effectiveness of School Learning Action Cell (LAC) among secondary schools in Northwest District of the City Schools Division of Ilagan* (Unpublished manuscript). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888572>
- Grape, J. C. (2024). Learning Action Cell in professional development: Teachers' perspective. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*. <https://www.ijfmr.com>
- Hendrickx, M. M. H. G., Thurlings, M. C. G., & den Brok, P. J. (2025). Teachers' collaborative knowledge building in professional learning communities: Connecting interaction patterns to learning gains. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 40(1), Article 39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-024-00938-y>
- Hirsch, S. E., Ely, E., Lloyd, J. W., & Isley, D. (2018). *Targeted professional development: A data-driven approach to identifying educators' needs*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1199818.pdf>
- Holmqvist, M., & Lelling, B. (2021). Teachers' collaborative professional development for inclusive education. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 36(5), 819–833. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2020.1842974>
- Husseina, J. W. (2017). The role of community of practice (CoP) to ensure teacher development and sense of professionalism: The implication for university teachers. *Bahir Dar Journal of Education*, 17(2).
- Ikpur, E., & Peter, G. O. (2024). Professional learning communities: A mechanism for enhancing teachers' professional agency. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 4(1), 1–12. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377383005_Professional_Learning_Communities_A_Mechanism_for_Enhancing_Teachers%27_Professional_Agency

- Irby, B. J., Lynch, J., Boswell, J., & Hewitt, K. K. (2017). Mentoring as professional development. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, 25(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13611267.2017.1312895>
- Juanite, M. L. Q., & Ardiente, M. R. M. (2025). Lived experiences of teachers and school heads on Learning Action Cell (LAC). *EPRA International Journal of Environmental Economics, Commerce and Educational Management*, 12(6). North Eastern Mindanao State University, Surigao del Sur, Philippines. <https://eprajournals.com>
- Karlen, Y., Bäuerlein, K., & Brunner, S. (2024). Teachers' assessment of self-regulated learning: Linking professional competences, assessment practices, and judgment accuracy. *Social Psychology of Education*, 27(2), 461–491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-023-09845-4>
- Khasawneh, Y. J. A., Alsarayreh, R., Al Ajlouni, A. A., Eyadat, H. M., Ayasrah, M. N., & Khasawneh, M. A. S. (2023). An examination of teacher collaboration in professional learning communities and collaborative teaching practices. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 10(3), 446–452. <https://doi.org/10.20448/jeelr.v10i3.4841>
- Koci, A. (2025). Transformational leadership in education: Managing institutional reforms for curriculum modernization. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 6(3), 2347–2351. <https://doi.org/10.55248/gengpi.6.0325.1178>
- Kraft, M. A., & Blazar, D. (2017). Individualized coaching to improve teacher practice across grades and subjects: New experimental evidence. *Educational Policy*, 31(7), 1033–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904816631099>
- Kraft, M. A., Bolves, A., & Hurd, N. M. (2021). *School-based mentoring relationships and human capital formation (EdWorkingPaper No. 21-441)*. Annenberg Institute at Brown University. [https://doi.org/10.26300/96bs-6m26**\[1\]](https://doi.org/10.26300/96bs-6m26**[1])
- Krille, C. (2020). *Teachers' participation in professional development: A systematic review*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-38844-7>
- Kutsyuruba, B., & Godden, L. (2019). The role of mentoring and coaching as a means of supporting the well-being of educators and students. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, 8(4), 229–234. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMCE-12-2019-081>
- Lactam, M. Q. (2023). Implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and its monitoring & evaluation strategies employed by teachers and school heads in the Division of Occidental Mindoro, Philippines. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(11), 2157–2161. <https://doi.org/10.55248/gengpi.4.1123.113119>
- Laureano, H. B., & Manalang, A. C. (2023). Coaching and mentoring practices of master teachers. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(7), 333–358. <https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/1-IJAMS-JULY-2023-333-358.pdf>
- Levine, T. H., Mitoma, G. T., Anagnostopoulos, D. M., & Roselle, R. (2022). Exploring the nature, facilitators, and challenges of program coherence in a case of teacher education program redesign using core practices. *Journal of Teacher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00224871221108645>
- Li, Z., Chen, J., & Li, Q. (2025). The relationship between teacher professional development and students' social and emotional skills: Examining the mediating roles of teacher self-efficacy and teaching

- practices. *Current Psychology: A Journal for Diverse Perspectives on Diverse Psychological Issues*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-025-08031-3>
- Lo Iacono, V. (2025, August 23). *5 key principles of Knowles' adult learning theory and using it in the workplace*. Symonds Research. <https://symondsresearch.com/malcolm-knowles-adult-learning-theory/>
- Ma, X., & Marion, R. (2024). How does leadership affect teacher collaboration? Evidence from teachers in US schools. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 35(2), 116–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2024.2330533>
- Madel, R., & Zimmerman, N. (2024). *Peer mentoring for professional growth and sustainability: A model for support, leadership, and learning*. ERIC. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1469600.pdf>
- Magundayao, F. C. (2024). Effectiveness of School Learning Action Cell (LAC) among secondary schools in Northwest District of the City Schools Division of Ilagan. *International Conference on Contemporary Education, Psychology and Health*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888572>
- Maraza-Quispe, B. (2024). Impact of the use of gamified online tools: A study with Kahoot and Quizizz in the educational context. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 14(1), 132–140. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2024.14.1.2033>
- Marcelo, M. C. A. (2023). *Master teachers: Providing technical assistance, coaching, and mentoring to fellow teachers*. Orani National High School – Parang Parang. <https://www.depedbataan.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/MASTER-TEACHERS-PROVIDING-TECHNICAL-ASSISTANCE-COACHING-AND-MENTORING-TO-FELLOW-TEACHERS.pdf>
- Meidelina, O., Saleh, A. Y., Cathlin, C. A., & Winesa, S. A. (2023). Transformational leadership and teacher well-being: A systematic review. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, 17(3), 417–424. <https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v17i3.20858>
- Mertens, D. M. (2020). *Research and evaluation in education and psychology: Integrating diversity with quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods* (5th ed.). SAGE.
- Misana, L. S., Njiku, J. F., & Mwaihola, M. O. (2025). Exploring the social, instrumental, academic, personal, and professional identities of peer mentoring experiences among preservice teachers. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, 33(1), 45–61. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13611267.2024.2420123>
- Moises, R. D., & Maguate, G. S. (2023). School Learning Action Cell and professional development. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 6(7), 127–133. <http://www.ijlrhss.com/paper/volume-6-issue-7/17-HSS-2126.pdf>
- Morales, J. S., & Marquez, M. F. (2025). Strengthening teachers' innovativeness through transformational leadership educational reform framework. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 11(8). <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra23595>
- Morris, J. E., Lummis, G. W., Lock, G., Ferguson, C., Hill, S., & Nykiel, A. (2020). The role of leadership in establishing a positive staff culture in a secondary school. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(5), 802–820. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143219864937>

- Mulay, I. K. (2025). Professional advancement through School Learning Action Cell (SLAC): Insights of secondary school teachers. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 10(5), 4114–4117. <https://doi.org/10.38124/ijisrt/25may1935>
- Nuqui, A. V., & Rivera, J. R. (2021). Professional learning communities: A framework for teacher collaboration and student success in Philippine schools. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 9(6), 123–134.
- Ó Ceallaigh, T. J., & Connolly, C. (2024). Navigating transformative assessment and feedback in teacher education: Unveiling challenges and innovative practices. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 47(2), 197–203. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2024.2352816>
- Pacaol, N. F. (2021). Teacher's workload intensification: A qualitative case study of its implications on teaching quality. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 8(1), 43–60. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348137005>
- Padillo, G. G., Manguilimotan, R., Capuno, R., & Espina, R. C. (2021). Professional development activities and teacher performance. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(3), 497–506. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.61.2021.93.497.506>
- Pappas, C. (2025, October 2). *The adult learning theory: Andragogy of Malcolm Knowles*. eLearning Industry. <https://elearningindustry.com/the-adult-learning-theory-andragogy-of-malcolm-knowles>
- Park University. (2025, February 14). *Adult learning theory: How adults learn differently*. <https://www.park.edu/blog/adult-learning-theory-how-adults-learn-differently/>
- Patfield, S., Gore, J., & Harris, J. (2023). Shifting the focus of research on effective professional development: Insights from a case study of implementation. *Journal of Educational Change*, 24, 345–363. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-021-09446-y>
- Patrick, S. K. (2022). Collaborating for improvement? Goal specificity and commitment in targeted teacher partnerships. *Teachers College Record*, 124(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/01614681221086104>
- Prudente, M. S., Ballado-Tan, M. A., & del Rosario, R. C. (2024). *Systematic review of professional development programs for teachers in the Philippines*. Education Commission 2. https://edcom2.gov.ph/media/2024/02/18_Prudente-et-al-Systematic-Review-of-Professional-1.pdf
- Quimio, J. (2025). School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) among secondary public school teachers in the Municipality of Daraga. *International Journal of Education, Business and Economics Research (IJEBER)*, 5(3), 1–35. https://ijeber.com/uploads2025/ijeber_05_333.pdf
- Rajaram, K. (2021). Learning interventions: Collaborative learning, critical thinking and assessing participation real-time. In *Evidence-based teaching for the 21st century classroom and beyond* (pp. 77–120). Springer. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-33-6804-0_3
- Reños, G., & Pontillas, P. (2024). Classroom observation and teachers' professional development activities: Basis for intervention plan. *American Journal of Arts and Human Science*, 3(3), 71–93. <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajahs.v3i3.3077>
- Richardson, L. (2024). The role of educational leadership in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes. *Academy of Educational Leadership Journal*, 28(S2), 1–2. <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/the-role-of-educational-leadership-in-enhancing-student-engagement-and-learning-outcomes-17353.html>

- Sales, B. B. (2024). Exploring the Learning Action Cell implementation and its challenges in public elementary schools. *Technoarete Transactions on Advances in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4(1), 1–10. <https://technoaretepublication.org/socialsciences-humanities/article/exploring-the-learning-action-cell.pdf>
- Sandoval-Rios, F., Gajrdo-Poblete, C., & Lopez-Nuñez, J. A. (2025). Role of data literacy training for decision-making in teaching practice: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Education*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2025.1485821>
- Sanusi, N., Zulkifli, H., Hamzah, M. I., & Jait, K. (2025). Professional development in classroom assessment: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, 19(4), 2220–2228. <https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v19i4.22026>
- Schelling, N., & Rubenstein, L. D. (2021). Elementary teachers' perceptions of data-driven decision-making. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability*, 33(2), 317–344. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-021-09356-w>
- Silva, V. C. (2021). School Learning Action cell as a key for teacher's continuous learning and development. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 4(8). <https://journal.ijresm.com/index.php/ijresm/article/view/1141>
- Smith, J. A., Flowers, P. & Larkin, M. (2021). *Interpretative phenomenological analysis theory, method, and research*. Sage Publications.
- Smith, R., & Hayes, S. (2022). A critical review of the use of Wenger's community of practice framework in professional learning. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 12(3), 112–128. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1140262.pdf>
- Smith, S. U., Hayes, S., & Shea, P. (2017). A critical review of the use of Wenger's community of practice (CoP) theoretical framework in online and blended learning research, 2000-2014. *Online Learning*, 21(1), 209-237. doi: 10.24059/olj.v21i1.963
- Sumampong, R. V., & Arnado, A. A. (2024). The influence of transformational leadership on teacher motivation and engagement: Proposed TELM framework. *Educational Administration Theory and Practice*, 30(5). <https://doi.org/10.53555/kuvey.v30i5.2009>
- Suphasri, P., & Chinokul, S. (2021). Reflective practice in teacher education: Issues, challenges, and considerations. *PASAA: Journal of Language Teaching and Learning in Thailand*, 62, 109–128. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1334998.pdf>
- To, J., Panadero, E., & Carless, D. (2022). A systematic review of the educational uses and effects of exemplars. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 47(8), 1167–1182. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2021.2011134>
- Tobin, B., Farren, M., & Crotty, Y. (2024). Impacting teaching and learning through collaborative reflective practice. *Educational Action Research*. Advance Online Publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09650792.2024.2394933>
- Tomogon, J. A. N., & Lactam, J. Y. (2024). School Learning Action Cell (SLAC): Relationship in promoting teachers' instructional mastery and pedagogical efficacy. *Dinkum Journal of Social Innovations*, 3(3). <https://www.dinkumpublishers.com/djsi/d-0299/>
- Trube, M. B., Dominguez, N., & Martinez, W. (Eds.). (2024). The value of mentoring for leadership development. *The Chronicle of Mentoring & Coaching*, 8(4). <https://doi.org/10.62935/f0710p>

- Uy, F. T., Andrin, G. R., Vestal, P. E., & Malbas, M. H. (2024). Transformative leadership in Philippine education: Fostering innovation and excellence. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence*, 1(3). <https://risejournals.org/index.php/imjrise/article/view/203>
- Vedder-Weiss, D., Tractenberg-Maslaton, R., & Sarfati-Shaulov, K. (2025). Facilitation strategies responding to emotional displays in PD discourse: Navigating relational and learning goals. *Instructional Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-025-09737-4>
- Virgana, V., & Fitriani, A. (2025). Transformative leadership: Cultivating teacher excellence through satisfaction, environment, and self-efficacy. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, 19(2), 1065–1073. <https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v19i2.21837>
- Watkins, K. E., Marsick, V. J., & Wasserman, I. (2019). Action research, action learning, and appreciative inquiry: Interventions that build individual and group capacity for EBOCD. In R. G. Hamlin, A. D. Ellinger, & J. Jones (Eds.), *Evidence-based initiatives for organizational change and development* (pp. 76–92). Business Science Reference/IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-6155-2.ch004>
- Welsh, R. O. (2024). Administering discipline: An examination of the factors shaping school discipline practices. *Education and Urban Society*, 56(7), 847–880. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00131245231208170>
- Wenger-Trayner, E., & Wenger-Trayner, B. (2025). *Communities of practice: A brief introduction*. Wenger-Trayner. <https://www.wenger-trayner.com/communities-of-practice/>
- White, H., & Drew, S. (2021). *Communities of practice as a social theory of learning: A conversation with Etienne Wenger-Trayner*. White Rose Research Online. <https://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/id/eprint/92950/3/repository11.pdf>
- Wilson, A. (2016). From professional practice to practical leader: Teacher leadership in professional learning communities. *International Journal of Teacher Leadership*, 7(2). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345312136_From_Professional_Practice_to_Practical_Leader_Teacher_Leadership_in_Professional_Learning_Communities
- Wisniewski, B., & Zierer, K. (2021). Functions and success conditions of student feedback in the development of teaching and teachers. In W. Rollett, H. Bijlsma, & S. Röhl (Eds.), *Student feedback on teaching in schools: Using student perceptions for the development of teaching and teachers* (pp. 125–138). Springer Nature Switzerland AG. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75150-0_8
- Wolf, K., & Stevens, E. (n.d.). The role of rubrics in advancing and assessing student learning. *The Journal of Effective Teaching*. <https://www.ucdenver.edu/docs/librariesprovider8/default-document-library/role-of-rubrics.pdf>
- Zulfqar, A., Valcke, M., Quraishi, U., & Devos, G. (2021). Developing academic leaders: Evaluation of a leadership development intervention in higher education. *SAGE Open*, 11(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244021991815>